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THE REAL ESTATE MARKET AND LAND RENTAL IN CUBA:
AN ANALYSIS OF THE PROPERTY MARKET
IN HAVANA, 2013-2019^{2*}

Keywords: *Cuba, socialism, real estate market, updating Cuba socialism, ground rent.*

Ключевые слова: *Куба, социализм, рынок недвижимости, обновление кубинского социализма, аренда земли*

Расширенная аннотация статьи на русском языке³

Цель настоящего документа – проанализировать появление земельной ренты в Гаване, после открытия в 2011 году кубинского рынка недвижимости, и обсудить ее последствия для кубинского социалистического перехода.

Рынок недвижимости на Кубе был запрещен в рамках процесса, проводимого в соответствии с Законом о реформе городов, опубликованным революционным правительством в 1960 году. Однако в 2011 году в результате процесса обновления кубинской социалистической модели была вновь разрешена торговля домами. Его появление восстановило рыночные механизмы и профессии, которые были ограничены в течение последних 60 лет, т.е. брокеры и нотариусы недвижимости. Тем не менее на рынке недвижимости по-прежнему действуют особые ограничения для предотвращения спекуляции недвижимостью, запрещающие покупку жилья иностранцами и владение более чем одним домом на семью. Однако развитие рынка недвижимости принесло новые социальные отношения, которые станут предметом этой статьи.

Для понимания динамики недвижимости с 2013 по 2019 год собрана база объявлений домов в Гаване, предоставляющая информацию об объявленной локализации домов, цене и характеристиках. Из анализа этой базы данных были вы-

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* **JEL codes:** P25, R32.

Citation: Alina Marcondes Miglioli (2021). Real-estate market and ground rent in Cuba: observations about the Havanese real-estate market between 2013 and 2019, *Problems in Political Economy*, 3 (27): 205-219.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5554182 (<https://zenodo.org/record/5554182>)

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делены два явления: корреляция между более высокими ценами и пригодностью домов для коммерческого использования в автономной частной работе; и различия между ценами на жилые помещения, например, цены на жилые помещения, расположенные в туристических районах, являются более высокими. В общем, чем более близкое местоположение к туристической деятельности у дома, тем выше его цена. Поэтому рынок недвижимости сегментирован среди существующего жилого фонда в Гаване: дома, построенные до революции и расположенные в центре города, являются самыми дорогими. Основная коммерческая деятельность, осуществляемая в этих домах, была определена как аренда помещений для туристов и услуг ресторана и столовой, чему способствовало увеличение числа кубинско-американских посетителей в течение последнего десятилетия.

Возможность частного распределения прибыли, полученной в результате осуществления хозяйственной и туристической деятельности домовладельцами, требует анализа социалистического накопления, основанного на подходе политической экономии. В статье мы говорим о том, что с теоретической точки зрения можно применять категории политической экономии к обществу в условиях социалистического перехода, потому что Закон ценности до сих пор действует, хотя со спецификой того, что избыточная стоимость в основном присваивается и распределяется государством.

Чтобы интерпретировать наблюдаемые явления, мы использовали теорию земельной ренты, разработанную Марксом, и теорию марксистской городской ренты, разработанную Джарамилло (2003). Согласно Марксу, цена земли отражает право владельца земли на соответствующую арендную плату на землю, поэтому цены земли соответствуют его будущей арендной плате, доведенной до текущей стоимости. В свою очередь, земельная арендная плата возникает в связи с правом землевладельца распределять излишки прибыли от производства, осуществляемого на его земле, в связи с чем арендная плата может возникать в виде различий в производительности или монопольных цен в зависимости от конкретных условий эксплуатации.

По словам Джарамилло, в городах аренда земли может быть присвоена в два момента: при строительстве и продаже жилья в качестве конечного товара, и при использовании городского пространства. В последнем случае арендная плата за землю зависит от избыточной прибыли, обусловленной использованием конкретных площадей. Таким образом, арендная плата за землю, взимаемая в жилых помещениях, отражает экономию затрат на воспроизводство рабочей силы, в то время как в коммерческих помещениях арендная плата за землю стремится компенсировать излишки прибыли, возникающие в результате более высокой скорости ротации капитала в этом районе. С этой точки зрения, различия в ценах между кварталами Гаваны свидетельствуют о появлении дифференцированной арендной платы за землю, связанной с изменением использования площадей в домах, расположенных в туристических кварталах: от использования жилья до коммерческого использования.

Полученные результаты свидетельствуют о новых проблемах и вызовах для целей кубинской революции. Во-первых, частная арендная плата за землю создает неравные отношения, в которых некоторые кубинцы могут получить часть ресурсов, генерируемых туристической деятельностью, поскольку их дома находятся в

туристических районах. Этот факт приводит к противоречию между все возрастающей тенденцией распределения доходов частного туризма и социалистическим проектом на Кубе. Во-вторых, предполагается наличие внутреннего неравенства, поскольку кубинцы сталкиваются с различными возможностями для самозанятости в зависимости от расположения своих домов. Третье следствие может быть связано со специализацией и пространственной дифференциацией территории, что через рынок недвижимости усиливает коммерческое и жилое развитие некоторых районов. Это новое условие также требует внимания, чтобы не допустить его превращения в какую-то городскую сегрегацию.

В этой статье делается вывод о том, что эти три фактора являются основными социальными последствиями, наблюдаемыми в результате появления кубинского рынка недвижимости и получения доходов от туризма в виде арендной платы за землю.

Introduction

In 2011, a series of measures were adopted in Cuba aiming to update Cuban socialism. Among them was the return of the real estate market after sixty years of its prohibition. In capitalist societies, the commodification of housing is related to urban ground rent and its social effects, such as price speculation and spatial segregations. Therefore, the restoration of the real estate market may bring back those phenomena to Cuba, despite the measures and legislation created to avoid it. Considering Cuba during a socialist transition, when the permanence of capitalist social relations relies on contradiction to the socialization of the means of production (Bettelheim, 1975), the possibility of ground rent capture poses new issues about the influence of ground rent in social distribution and what is their significance to the Cuban socialist project.

This article aims to describe and analyse the emergence of ground rent capture after the reopening of the real estate market in 2011. To this end, the article is organized in five sections in addition to this introduction: the first recovers the history of Urban Reform in Cuba and the demercantilisation of housing in the first 60 years of the revolution; the second portrays the re-emergence of the real estate market after 2011; the third analyses the dynamics of the real estate market between 2013 and 2019; the fourth reflects on the origins of ground rent and the final section brings some considerations on the observed events.

The demercantilisation of housing

In 1959, when the Cuban Revolution triumphed, the housing situation was precarious in rural and urban areas. Therefore, housing was one of the major problems for Cuban workers. In the countryside, sugar industry workers were living in *bohíos* – a type of straw dwellings with earthen floors used originally by pre-Columbian populations (Segre, 1980). They had no electricity, sanitation, or running water. The housing situation in the cities was also poor, as most urban workers lived in tenements, where each family occupied a small room and shared the kitchen and bathroom with other families. For these reasons, the hygienic condition in those buildings was precarious and a large number of them were in poor condition (Acosta, Hardoy, 1973).

The housing problem also encompassed ownership insecurity, as most Cuban workers lived in rented accommodation, charged with high rents compared with the average

workers' wage resulting in many daily evictions. In Republican Cuba, the main economic activity of the national bourgeoisie was renting; consequently, no effort was directed towards the national construction industry. In turn, popular house construction has not developed, and neither a mortgage system. The bourgeoisie's specialization in rent-seeking activities has developed as the outcome of its displacement from the sugar production after the North American bourgeoisie had appropriated the national sugar mills during the imperialist assault on the island in 1902 and 1929. Since then, the Cuban bourgeoisie began to participate in the process of capital accumulation through the extraction of ground rent: in the countryside, they rented out the land to international sugar companies; in the cities, they transformed its old colonial dwellings into tenements and rented them out to urban workers (Vasconcelos, 2016).

The Cuba Revolution was accomplished by the efforts made by the 26th of July Revolutionary Movement (MR26-7) – and its nationalist historical tradition headed by the Revolutionary Cuban Party (PRC) – against President Batista. In the early political agenda of the revolutionary movement, the severity of the housing problems appears as one of its main complaints, thus one of its main demands were the reduction and control of rents and evictions (Castro, 1953). Therefore, only 26 days after the overthrow of President Batista the evictions were banned and three months later rents were reduced by 50%.

By the time these measures were approved, the urban problems began to be discussed in greater depth and the government became aware that the Cuban housing problem relied on real estate speculation. Hence, to eradicate it, the causes of urban speculation had to be addressed. To this extent, the Urban Reform Law (1960) was published acknowledging that the rent-seeking activities and the concentration of housing production in the hands of the bourgeoisie were the main causes of the high rental prices and the lack of affordable popular housing for sale. Following the socialist ambition of the Cuban Revolution, the Urban Reform aimed to demercantilize housing by implementing five major measures: i) prohibiting the house's purchase, sale, and renting; ii) nationalizing of all housing stock and vacant lots; iii) establishing the price of vacant lot prices in CUP 4 per square meter; iv) centralizing the housing provision in the State; and v) promptly distributing the entire housing stock to its current occupants, at a price corresponding to maximum 10% of their family income (CUBA, 1961).

By the end of the decade, the Urban Reform managed to remove the commercial aspect of housing and to overcome the housing deficit through the distribution of the existing housing stock, the construction of new dwellings, and the conversion of vacant commercial or productive buildings into dwellings. However, its long-term goal of distributing free state housing when the productive forces have fully developed was not achieved, due to the difficulty to overcome underdevelopment and the necessity to assign resources to other economic sectors. As a consequence, the responsibility of housing construction gradually returned to the citizens, initially through the micro-brigade movement¹ and later through self-construction. Currently, the state is in charge only for the construction of so-

¹ The micro-brigades were task forces made up of 33 workers considered outstanding in their workplaces and temporarily allocated to construction sites to build homes and urban services. More than 82,000 homes were constructed, which was possible due to the standard solutions using precast components and an advanced industrialized methodology, developed in a precast factory donated by the URSS in 1963. Despite the labour reallocation problem, micro-brigades also met the subjective agenda of the revolutionary government to strengthen the revolutionary spirit by sharing the responsibilities and effort throughout the population (Mathey, 1989; Segre, 1980).

cial housing, distributed to the people in vulnerable social conditions (i.e.: single mothers, people with disability or affected by natural disasters). Housing remained isolated from the private market from 1960 to 2011. However, in 1985 a housing exchange tool was developed, the *permutas*, which allowed people to swap equivalent houses, provided that the transaction did not involve any monetary counterpart (Nunez, 2012).

The re-mercantilization of housing

The real estate market was released in 2011 by Decree-Law 288, as an outcome of the process of updating the Cuban socialist model, an attempt to modernize the socialist system following the new national and international context after the end of URSS and the economic crises that preceded it. The changes made to endure this new scenario included strengthening tourism and biomedicine to become a strategic sector of the Cuban economy and relieving some of the State responsibilities to private initiative, such as the provision for all consumer goods. However, the process does not correspond itself to a transition towards the capitalist mode of production. In fact, it rather reflects the necessity to implement changes to suit the new economic and social composition of Cuban society.

The necessity of modernizing and updating Cuban socialism also corresponded to the political demand of strengthening Raul Castro's government. In 2007, when Raul became president, his political proposal was to meet the constrained demands of the prior period and attend the claim for greater popular participation in the government decisions. Thus, the political process of elaborating the updating guidelines began with the publication of a document by the Cuban Communist Party with some suggestions for the economic and social policy reforms; subsequently, this document was largely discussed in public meetings held by neighbourhood and work centers, where the additions and complaints were collected and organized. Those were discussed and systematized by the delegates of the 6th Communist Party Congress, and added or modified on the original document, whose outcome is known as «Guidelines for Updating the Model of Cuban Socialism».

The authorization for the free purchase and sale of housing was one of the elements added on the popular discussion stage. Its popular demand reflected the spatial immobility and desire to move, as families complained to be attached to the same house distributed during the urban reform sixty years ago. It was also believed that redistribution of the housing stock through the market would solve part of the housing problem, considered to be the poor distribution of the housing stock among households. Even though the composition of the family nuclei had changed since 1959, the buildings where they lived remained the same.

After the re-commodification of housing in 2011, some constraints were imposed due to avoid the return of real estate market speculation, such as the restrictions of owning one housing unit and one leisure house per each Cuban family, the allowance of homeownership only to Cuban residents, or naturalized foreigners, and the prohibition to build a house for sale purpose. Among Cubans, renting a house for living purposes is still prohibited. However, renting rooms for tourists was allowed early in 1993 when the self-employment sector was created. According to self-employment legislation, it is possible to rent rooms or the entire house to accommodate tourists or to perform other commercial activities, such as restaurants or coffee shops. Nevertheless, to perform

these activities it is necessary to have a license issued by the government, which implied on the correspondent payment of taxes and duties on income, which are applied to inhibit capital accumulation from private initiative.

The Decree-Law 288 established that the purchase and sale of housing can be carried out by Cuban residents or nationalized foreigners. The price must be agreed upon by both parties and the transactions must be registered before a *notary*, which is a government correspondent with notary functions, and taxed according to the tax law. The transactions must be paid in full and must take place through the Cuban banking system, that is, with a deposit made into a current account in the name of the former owner. The possibility of free price-setting reveals the Cubans' preferences among the housing available on the market and the observation on the charged price dynamics demonstrate some particularities about the functioning of this real estate market.

Real Estate Dynamics

To observe the price dynamics of the Cuban real estate market, we collected and analysed the data of houses for sale in Havana published on four Cuban real estate websites between 2013 and 2019¹. Observation of price dynamics (Graph 1) over this period has led us to three main conclusions regarding the price level and its determinations over time, as described below.

Graph 1. Average Price of Dwelling and Average Price per Square Meter in Havana, 2013-2019.

Source: Detras de La Fachada. www.detrasdelafachada.com (Accessed in January 30, 2020); Zafiro. www.zafiroinmobiliaria.com (Accessed in January, 30 2020); Por el Techo. www.poreltetcho.com (Accessed in January 30, 2020); IslaSi. www.islasi.com (Accessed in January 30, 2020).

¹ Detras de La Fachada. www.detrasdelafachada.com (Accessed in January 30, 2020); Zafiro. www.zafiroinmobiliaria.com (Accessed in January, 30 2020); Por el Techo. www.poreltetcho.com (Accessed in January 30, 2020); IslaSi. www.islasi.com (Accessed in January 30, 2020).

The choice of using selling advertisements to build a database from the real estate market responds to the difficulty in gathering real estate data, since Cuban notaries, as in the rest of the world, rarely provide details of real estate transactions, as this information is considered private. Therefore, the data provided in the advertisements is the maximum acknowledge obtainable in the real estate market. The main problem in working with these advertisements is them overprice due to the expectations of further negotiations. To avoid this problem, we used the information obtained from websites of real estate companies, because unlike the advertisements in generic classified sites, they orient their clients about the prices practiced in the market in order to attract more offers.

i) The average price of housing in Cuba: who could afford it?

The results show a high price level of the houses advertised between 2013 and 2015, since the average housing price announced during that period was US\$66,000, as shown in Graph 1; the high level of housing prices is not compatible with Havana's average wage, that in 2016, for example, was CUP 776,00 (Onei, 2016), approximately US\$30,00 per month, or US\$358 per year. The discrepancy between these values is aggravated by the fact that there are no housing financing mechanisms in Cuba; however, we can still find three possible explanations for the high cost of housing in Cuba, as described below.

Firstly, the high price of housing reflects the premise that the real estate market serves solely to exchange properties among Cubans. Thus, it is assumed that all Cubans have a house that they can sell to buy a new one. In other words, it is not expected that Cubans should reach for their first home in the real estate market – since housing is still a social good – and neither that salary will be the source of income for housing purchasing. Nevertheless, the acquisition of a new house is still a complex and problematic process in Cuba, that relies firstly on purchasing from the State, which since the 90's economic crisis has prioritized granting housing for free to people in vulnerable conditions. The other possibility to secure a new house is through its self-construction, which faces the difficulty in access to construction materials, which became an obstacle due to the scarcity of imported materials, despite the subsidy policies. Therefore, due to the difficulties involved in the acquisition of a new house, the real estate market had indeed become a possible solution for its purchase.

Secondly, it must be considered that house values are following the income of the families that receive the remittances from relatives living abroad to complement their wages, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1
Relative share of wages and remittances in Cuban household income

	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
Wages	40%	37%	33%	30%	29%	32%	34%
Remittances	60%	63%	67%	70%	71%	68%	66%

Source: Available at: <http://www.thehavanaconsultinggroup.com/en-/Articles/Article/20#:~:text=From%202008%20to%202015%2C%20Cuban,remittances%20became%20legal%20in%201993.> (Accessed in February 2021).

In the last three decades, remittances have become an essential source of household income and consumption. Table 2 shows that the average population of Havana satisfies its consumption with imported products, which tends to increase along with family income. Thus, the greatest diversity of consumption requires access to foreign currency, which can be obtained in the employment of joint-ventures companies or through receive remittances from family abroad. The access to exclusive markets for those who have access to hard currencies reveals a new pattern of inequality in consumption. This dual monetary system is harmful to those relying on their wages, particularly in national currency, which became unable to access some markets, such as the housing market¹.

¹ This phenomenon corresponds to one of the side effects of monetary duality in Cuba, that implies in the devaluation of the national currency in comparison to the convertible currency. See Pavel, 2008.

Table 2
Sources of expenditures per type of currencies: La Habana, 2001

	Average	Lower wages	Higher wages
Source expenditures	100	100	100
In CUP	63,1	99,98	67,1
State Stores	15	44,21	12,1
Agricultural Market	32,3	33,41	39
Self-Employment	15,7	22,36	16
Work Centers	0,05	0	0
In CUC	36,9	0,02	32,9
Import shops	36,4	0,02	32,1
Self-Employment	0,5	0	0,8

Source: Cepal et. al., 2004.

A third and more inaccurate explanation about what may have influenced real estate prices relies on the changes in Cuba’s migration policy after 2012 that allowed Cubans living abroad, the expatriates, to move back to Cuba. Consequently, high housing prices may be related to the payment capacity of these Cubans who have large access to hard currency.

In conclusion, the high prices of the real estate market in comparison to the average Cuban wage seem to be related to previous homeownership and mainly to the access to foreign currency for both Cuban nationals and expatriates.

ii) Two real estate markets in one: housing and commercial use of housings.

From Graph 1, it is also possible to observe the increasing price trend between 2013 and 2016. The price peak in 2016 draws attention to the events in Cuba that year. In this regard, the investigations showed that the price hike in 2016 was related to the expectation of increased tourist activity in Havana following the rapprochement between the Cuban and US governments in 2015 when after almost six decades of closed borders between the two countries, negotiations between Raul Castro and Barack Obama resulted in the release of American tourism in Cuba. The immediate consequence of this resolution was the increase of US tourists on the island, especially Cuban Americans¹ (Graph 2).

Graph 2. Cuban-American tourists arrival in Cuba: 2013-2018.

Source: Onei, 2020.

¹ In this regard, it is possible to distinguish two profiles of Cuban Americans. Cubans in exile during or just after the Revolution do not travel to the island for ideological reasons, as they consider travel to Cuba to mean funding from the communist government. On the other hand, Cubans who emigrated after the 1990s did so for economic reasons, and they usually return to the island every year to see their relatives and friends again and to bring back goods and utensils for their families (Jolivet, 2018).

The arrival of Cuban Americans has reinforced the diversification of tourism in Cuba beyond “sun and beach” resorts towards architectural and city tourism. Therefore, it has also increased the expectation about urban tourism activities, such as accommodation in private homes – *casas particulares* – and private restaurants. Renting houses for tourists and providing food services in restaurants, coffee shops, candy shops and others is part of the set of activities authorized to operate privately as self-employed since 1993 in Cuba. Although this category of autonomous work – the *cuentalpropismo* – emerged as a short-term option to perform complementary activities during the period of economic crisis, it has evolved and currently can operate as a small and medium-sized business with private ownership of the means of production and labour recruitment. One of the peculiarities of *cuentalpropismo* is its performance in the domestic space. Thus, it is not uncommon for restaurants and coffee shops (as well as beauty salons, shoe shops, and others) to be set up in the workers’ living rooms and garages.

One of the most profitable activities for the self-employed is the tourist accommodation in “*casas particulares*”. Although rental among Cubans is forbidden, the temporary lodging service was authorized in 1997 to cope with the growing influx of tourists to Cuba, in face of the island’s low accommodation capacity. Since then, the activity has developed to the point of being complementary to «sun and beach» tourism, as it meets the demand of those interested in more ‘exotic’ experiences, especially after the AirBnB arrival in Cuba in 2015, which transformed the activity to become more professionalized and fit the standards of the platform.

The use of houses to perform a tourism-related economic activity is one of the main elements driving the price of houses in Havana during the analysed period. This phenomenon can be observed by the valorisation of certain residences that have an aesthetic more favourable to the tourist activity, known as the ‘capitalist’ houses. Originally the term ‘capitalist houses’ was created to differentiate the date of construction of the dwellings, assigning houses built before 1959 with the term ‘capitalist’. These houses are equally deteriorated by time as the rest of the housing stock. However, they are distinguished by the better quality of their construction materials and their historic and architectural design, which favours private tourism businesses.

Evidence of the preference for ‘capitalist houses’ can be noted by the differential price per square meter of houses built before and after the revolution (Graph 3). At the same time, in reading the content of the advertisements we can identify several passages in which capitalist houses are identified with the possibility of converting their space into small businesses for the self-employed, as it can be seen in the following excerpt¹.

From the reflections raised on the use of housing as a space to carry out productive and commercial activities, we can state that the Cuban real estate market is composed of two sub-markets, the housing and the commercial, and they are inseparable due to the economic activities carried out in domestic spaces.

¹ “Flat of 2 rooms, with 2 bathrooms, small kitchen, small living room, dining room, balconies, 6th floor, beautiful views of the malecon and the city, genial for rent equipped with everything for this business” [Freely translated from < <https://www.detrasdelaFachada.com/venta-apartamento-en-sn-lazaro-campanario-perseverancia-centro-habana-la-habana-cuba/kzf25ojtcn6nqhv>> Accessed in 2020]

Graph 3. Average price/m² of houses announced in Havana from 2013 to 2019 by their construction date: Pre-Revolutionary (<1959) and Revolutionary constructions (>1959)¹.

Source: Detras de La Fachada. www.detrasdelafachada.com (Accessed in January 30, 2020); Zafiro. www.zafiroinmobiliaria.com (Accessed in January, 30 2020); Por el Techo. www.poreltetcho.com (Accessed in January 30, 2020); IslaSi. www.islasi.com (Accessed in January 30, 2020).

iii) Spatial Differentiation: territorial consequences of house commodification.

The relationship between real estate prices and the tourism sector can also be observed territorially. In Map 1, we can see the disposal of the average square meter price during the period from 2013 to 2019 distributed by the municipalities of Havana. Unlike the capitalist countries, in Cuba public services are distributed throughout the territory, so all neighbourhoods and municipalities have equal access to urban facilities, such as schools and health centers (Image 1). Therefore, the preference for the coastal municipalities is more likely to be related to the tourism business that takes place in the municipalities of Old Havana, Centro Havana, Plaza de la Revolución, Playa, and Habana del Este. One could hypothesize that the higher price of housing is related to mobility conditions, i.e., housing located in coastal neighbourhoods would present advantages for being closer to tourist jobs. However, this hypothesis seems unlikely, given the low cost of municipal transportation in Cuba, about CUP 5, which corresponds to 19 US cents.

In Old Havana, Havana Centro and Plaza de la Revolución are located the greatest tourist attractions, as the colonial Royal Fortress Castle, the National Museum, Alicia Alonso Theatre, the Havana Cathedral, the Havana Port, and the picturesque streets of downtown Havana that have been revitalized by the Office of City Historian to welcome cruise ship tourists, and therefore contain international stores, museums, exhibitions, and local stores and restaurants. These elements can explain why despite the bad house deterioration, those neighbourhoods are better evaluated in the real estate market. In Plaza de la Revolución, there are the Coppelia ice cream parlour, the Havana Libre hotel, the Plaza de la Revolución, the National Library, and the National Zoo. In those municipalities, the buildings from the 1930s and 1950s have also made them attractive for

¹ The price values in 2018 were calculated by approximation following the high number of outliers on the database.

tourism. The Playa neighbourhood is further away from the tourist center; however, the large coastal mansions built by the Cuban bourgeoisie before the revolution and transformed into public agencies or embassies are a tourist attraction themselves. Hence, the neighbourhood has gained new tourist status after the installation of new hotels in the area. Finally, in Habana del Este there are the tourist beaches of Havana. Therefore, renting a “*casa particular*” located there has become an attractive option to “sun and beach” tourism, compared to the hotels and resorts located there (Scarpaci *et. al*, 2002).

Map 1. Average price per square meter by Havana Municipality – 2013-2019.

Source: Detras de La Fachada. www.detrasdelafachada.com (Accessed in January 30, 2020); Zafiro. www.zafiroinmobiliaria.com (Accessed in January, 30 2020); Por el Techo. www.poreltechto.com (Accessed in January 30, 2020); IslaSi. www.islasi.com (Accessed in January 30, 2020).

The physical transformations carried out in Old Havana to accommodate the touristic activities could be related to a kind of gentrification process, in which the original households are being displaced to promote international or national touristic business. This hypothesis cannot be completely ruled out; nevertheless, it should be observed that the urban renewal projects that take place in Havana are controlled and executed by the Office of the City Historian. This institution aims to promote urban renovation along with social projects. To do so, reforms for commercial use are attached to the community and social projects and local businesses are charged with a fee to subsidize the construction and renovation of new housing in the neighbourhood. This mechanism is expected to capture part of the profits and use them for renovation and construction with social interest.

Housing commodification and the emergence of urban land rent.

The conclusions observed in the section above can be interpreted from a political economy perspective. The conformation of two real estate markets and the difference among the houses due to their commercial or residential use call to a ground rent in-

interpretation. To this end, we will make a brief recovery on ground rent as elaborated by Marx and on further adaptations made by Jaramillo to analyse the Cuban reality.

From a Marxist political economy approach – and as defined by the Marxist Law of Value – the price of land could not be related to its value, because the land is not a product of human labour, and therefore it has no value. The land price reveals another social relation, that of private ownership of the land, and is hence determined by the net present value of ground rent. The ground rent corresponds to the appropriation of part of the surplus profit made by the most productive agricultural capitals, which is above the average profit realized at the least productive land. Marx recognized four types of rent that constitute the total ground rent: the absolute ground rent, the relative ground rents 1 and 2, and the monopoly ground rent. In short, differential rent derives from earning surplus profits on land with greater fertility or higher intensity of capital invested in comparison with the marginal land¹; the absolute ground is the rent obtainable merely from the private property of land²; and the monopoly rent presupposes the scarcity of a certain characteristic and physical condition, which makes the owner of this land the holder of a monopoly (Marx, 1867).

The interpretation from agricultural ground rent towards an urban ground rent requires a theoretical refinement because, unlike agricultural goods, the production of the urban land is the urban space, which is consumed in the same place where it is produced. Thus, it is possible to state that the extraction of urban land rent takes place in two spheres of articulation. The primary articulation relies on the production and selling of the built space as commodities. In this case, instead of fertility, what defines the differential rents is the different «constructability» among the urban space, that is, the facility of construction above those spaces. By constructability differentiation, we can interpret flat, dry land as being more expensive than sloping or waterlogged land. The second articulation corresponds to the commercialization of urban land use among residential, commercial, or industrial uses (Jaramillo, 2003).

The rent obtainable by each kind of urban space use has different determinations. In commercial areas, the ground rent is related to the surplus commercial profits due to the higher capital rotation on that specific location. Thus, landowners of urban land with greater access to consumers, better commercial infrastructure, and historical commercial use can charge a higher ground rent than on the marginal lands. In the case of housing, the differential urban rent emerges from the fact that the unequal distribution of urban services across space promote different labour force reproduction costs. This is due to the fact that the cost – in terms of money, time, and energy – of living away from schools, parks, facilities, and work are higher than those of living closer to these services. Therefore, better-located houses can be charged with ground rent corresponding to the “savings” from the reproduction costs³.

¹ On agricultural production, goods produced in the land with better fertility can charge lower prices than the market price – which is the price determined on the less fertile land. Therefore, an extra profit exists on this land, which can be appropriate by the landlord by the charge of a ground rent. For further explanation, see Marx (1867).

² The absolute ground rent depends on the different organic composition of capital among industrial and agricultural activities. For further explanation see chapter 45 (Marx, 1867).

³ Jaramillo (2003) also defines the industrial ground rent, determined by the surplus profit obtainable from industrial activities in some locations and the segregation ground rent, derived from the monopoly of social differentiation.

Thus, the urban land price corresponds to the present value of the absolute urban rent added to the rents of the first and second articulation, whereas the latter is commercial, residential, or industrial depending on which actively promotes the highest potential rent. For instance, if in a given space, the commercial land rent is higher than the residential one, only its value will integrate the total rent, inducing the specialization of commercial activity (Jaramillo, 2003).

Image 1. Health care facilities and medical research centers, Havana, late 1990s.

Source: Scarpaci et. al. 2002.

From this framework, it is possible to interpret what is happening in the Havanese real estate market. Considering the equal distribution of medical services (Image 1), schools, and work centers through the territory, residential ground rent seems to be similar among the different neighbourhoods. Thus, the differences in house prices seem to be related to the emergence of commercial differential income in Havana's tourist neighbourhoods. However, as commercial and residential activities take place in the same physical space, only the residents of these neighbourhoods can benefit from the possibility of absorbing both commercial and residential ground rent.

Final remarks

In this paper, we observed that the re-commodification of housing-related to self-employment and tourism provides a commercial ground rent for the owners of housing located in tourist districts. Assuming that the 'constructability' rent and urban residential rent are practically equivalent among the territory, it can be inferred that commercial rent pays an additional income for house owners located in the tourist districts. According to Marxist theory, in capitalist systems, ground rent results from a fundamental inequality: the private ownership of the land, which entitles its owners to

absorb part of the surplus value generated in the production process. However, what would it mean for the Cuban mode of production?

The answer to this question requires a more complex analysis since the phenomena portrayed concern only the city of Havana and it would be necessary to prove that they are occurring in other spaces in Cuba to give a comprehensive answer. That being said, we can only reflect on the meaning of what is happening in Havana. There, the different housing prices – related to different ground rental values – have the following consequences: firstly, they mean that some people can capture part of the resources generated by the tourist activity from the private ownership of the housing located in tourist areas. In other words, tourist activity considered a strategic sector for the Cuban economy, can have part of its profit appropriated privately in the form of commercial urban ground rent. The contradiction between the private appropriation of this income and the socialist project in Cuba has already been acknowledged. As a counterpart, a self-employment taxation system is in place to charge different rates according to the business, so the surplus profit related to localization can be recovered by direct taxation of the trader. At the same time, the taxation on real estate property transactions also includes different rates depending on the location of the building, transferring part of the ground rent to the state.

Secondly, despite the tax system, the practical consequence of the observed phenomenon is that Cubans face different opportunities to become self-employed depending on the location of their houses. For example, the residents of Boyeros do not have the same opportunities to take advantage of their houses to perform self-employment, and neither can they expect to acquire a house in the tourist centers from the sale of their property, since the difference in values between them is significant. This finding reveals a new challenge to the Cuban Revolution in dealing with this new source of inequality.

Finally, a third consequence can be named, the specialization and spatial differentiation of the territory, which through the real estate market, reinforces the commercial and residential vocation of some neighbourhoods. This new condition also requires attention to prevent it from turning into some kind of urban segregation.

The observed findings point to new problems and challenges to the Cuban Revolution. Without aiming to present generalist conclusions, our objective was to demonstrate that the return of the real estate market in the context of tourist specialization in Cuba has created new issues that need to be overcome to build socialism in an underdeveloped country, whose trajectory necessarily implies facing the contradictions in the development of the productive forces.

REFERENCES

- Acosta Maruja, Hardoy Jorge Henrique.* (1973) Urban reform in revolutionary Cuba. Yale University.
- Bettelheim C.* (1975) The transition to Socialist Economy. The Harverst Press.
- Castro Fidel.* (1953) La historia me absolverá. Ediciones Colihue SRL.
- Poítica social y reformas estructurales: Cuba a principios del siglo XXI.* (2004). Cepal; Inie; Pnud. – 352 p.

CUBA. (1961) Ley de Reforma Urbana.

Jaramillo Samuel. (2003) Los fundamentos económicos de la participación en plusvalías. Los Andes: CIDE.

Jolivet Violaine. (2018) Cuba Us- Relational Field: from a binational to a transnational urban perspective. Cuba Facing Forward: balancing identity and development in the twenty-first century.

Marx Karl. (1867) Capital: Volume 3: A Critique of Political Economy.

Mathey Kosta. (1989) Microbrigadas in Cuba: an unconventional response to the Housing Problem in a Latin American State. Habitat INTL. No 4. Volume 12. Pp. 55-62.

Nunez Ricardo H.A. (2012) Urban land management in Cuba. Radboud University. Department of Management Sciences.

Onei. (2017) Anuario Estadístico 2016: La Habana.

Pavel A. (2008) La encrucijada de la dualidad monetaria. Nueva Sociedad. No 128.

Scarpaci J., Segre R., Coyula M. (2002) Havana: two faces of the Antillean metropolis. The University of North Carolina Press.

Segre Roberto. (1980) La vivienda en Cuba en el siglo XX: República y Revolución.

Vasconcelos Joana Salém. (2016) História agrária da revolução cubana. São Paulo: Alameda.